

Chironomid, corixid, and ostracod pests of irrigated rice seedling roots

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We collected several aquatic arthropods in IRRI fields and kept them in glass aquaria to determine if they fed on rice. Two-week-old rice seedlings were suspended on foam sheets with their roots in the water. Three groups of aquatic invertebrates fed on rice roots —larvae (see figure) of seven species of chironomid midges dominated by *Chironomus kiiensis* Tokunaga, nymphs and adults of a corixid water boatman *Micronecta quadristrigata* Breddin, and adult ostracod crustacean *Cypris* sp.

We evaluated damage at 0, 20, 40, 100, and 500 arthropods per seedling for 72 h. The corixid cut more root hairs, but damage did not increase beyond 20adults/seedling. Chironomid and ostracod damage increased progressively with higher densities. Chironomid larvae damaged roots more than ostracods at equal densities. In the field, dapog-raised seedlings are particularly vulnerable to root damage because before transplanting, they grow for 2 weeks on banana leaves without soil.

Injury to rice seedling roots caused by chironomid midge larvae (arrow).